

Cellphone Addiction and Interpersonal Skills among Youth

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Abstract:- The current research aimed to explore the relationship between Cell phone Addiction and Interpersonal Skills among Pakistani Young Adults in a quantitative correlation research survey design. A purposive convenient sampling technique was used to approach $N= 251$ young adults (Males $n=102$ & Female $n=149$) age ranged between 18-35 years old, from different government and private institutes and universities of Karachi. It was hypothesized that there will be a negative relationship between Cell phone Addiction and Interpersonal skills. The findings revealed a significant weak positive relationship exists between cell phone addiction and interpersonal skills, ($r=.18$) and productive usage of cell phone ($r= .11$). The value of Cronbach's Alpha for Cellphone addiction is 0.79 and Interpersonal skills are 0.76, which lies in good range. The value of skewness and kurtosis shows that data is normally distributed. The significant value of interpersonal skill ($p= .73$) and cell phone addiction is ($p = .19$). Hence the roles of cell phone addiction levels were evaluated in link of interpersonal skills. The study is seen to have multiple implications, particularly in the field of education, counseling, training and mentoring of adults.

I. INTRODUCTION

Life in this era, have become highly dependent on the technology. Throughout the years with the advancements in technology, it has changed the ways of life we live, the way to communicate, the way to learn, the way of adaptability and so many perspectives with these continuous technological advancements. Talking about the process and developments in communication, with the inventions it has evolved over the years from one level to another. Moreover, it has been found that people who are shy and lonely are more likely to have cell phone addiction. Cell phone have become a most popular mobile device, now a day's almost every individual owns a cell phone. The trend of having multiple apps specially to carry out conversations, snaps, texting and calls have been become very easily accessible (Okazaki & Hirose, 2009).

(Salehan and Negahban, 2013) investigated the social networking on cell phones. When people become addicted to social networking applications it ultimately results in cell phone addiction. Thus, social networking sites do a major part in mobile addiction. So basically, these new technology purposes quickly for more tools of communication but on the other side making human interaction slow.

With the usage of cell phones and smart phones the communication styles have been rapidly changed the appearance of talking; now people are more likely to deal with each other through using cell phones at anytime and anywhere (Oulasvirta, Rattenbury, Ma, & Raita, 2011).

Hence, it can be assumed that excessive use of cell phones is affecting adversely on the social communication and giving a problem of nervousness and anxious outlook without cell phone, in daily life.

Cell phones are now changed into smart phones, which are more capable of advance features as compared to cell phones. Smart phones are operated by a system that runs applications on it. But cell phone and smart phones both used for communication and information seeking, though the medium of attaining that information may differ. With the more use of cell phones, youngsters are risking in their well-being, and development of skills. People prefer interaction on cell phones other than to meet with skills that required interpersonal skills which bound their practices of skills in their daily life.

Due to excessive use of cell phone people do not interact with each other and that is why unable to develop their relation. While individuals having effective interpersonal skills and psychosocial competencies are good in making better understanding of decision making, problem solving, critical thinking and communication that can courage healthy relationships, empathy for others and managing coping strategies with their lives in a productive manner.

It has become a trend in young adults to receive and send text messages as part of managing a connection. Texting influences in young adulthood relationships with their family and friends by being absence mentally in physically being there, because it particularly harms the relationship with parents and siblings. According to (Subrahmanyam and Greenfield, 2008), electronic multitasking "has become pervasive, sometimes to the expense of face to face family interaction, among siblings as well as parents". People belonging in young adulthood are more renowned to use cell phones to screen calls from parents and to disturb family meal time, vacations and rituals (Subrahmanyam & Greenfield, 2008).

Some studies showed that effects of texting are just for time being, but texting has become inevitable for general public. Young adults, with the rise in technology prefer to do contact with others through electronic gadgets rather than face to face communication. So, vitality of personal meetings is decreasing gradually.

Individuals feel a difficult time being present in a moment of time because of constant stream of text messages. It's so challenging to gain adults full attention when they are inclined towards using cell phone and looking down constantly at their cell phones to read messages. That are the main reason adults are less likely to hold their

presence in face to face conversations, family time/gathering, homework or other fun activities.

Research suggests that typically there is an emotional investment and connection with the cell phone that makes it seem like an extension of the self (Skog 2002; Taylor and Harper 2002; Green 2003; Ling and Yttri 2002; Vincent 2005; Martensen 2006; Caron and Caronia 2007). According to Sahu and Gupta (2016) the means of communication have been changed and hence have affected the interpersonal skills. As people now communicate through electronic devices like cell phones and has impaired one of the key components of interpersonal skills. Not only that cell phone addiction has minimized the individual interaction with each other's as even people sitting in front of each other are busy on their cell phone hence their interpersonal skill development or the practice of interpersonal skills is being inhibited.

Interpersonal relations are regulated by our code of conduct, customs and values in agreement. These relations are basis of society. There are multiple reasons why we interact with others or want to be participating in interaction with others.

As mentioned above due to excessive use of cell phone, people do not interact with each other and that is why unable to develop their relation. So, it can be concluded that due to cell phone addiction the process of relationship for that is the basic goal of interpersonal skill is affected which consequently ruins the process of skill development and its execution. Therefore, it is direly needed that these constructs be studied in indigenous perspective. Findings and their implications are discussed that educational institute can create insight into adults' mind about a possible relationship between adults and cell phone usage. Teach them timeouts for the family in the evening and on the weekends can increase their interpersonal skills and reduce their cell phone usage. It was being hypothesized that there is a negative relationship between cell phone addiction and interpersonal skills among young adults. Though, the results indicated weak positive relationship ($r=.18$) between the two variables which did not support the hypothesis.

II. METHOD

A. Research Design

The present study is quantitative correlational survey research design in which two structured self-report Questionnaire were used to evaluate the relationship between Cellphone Addiction and Interpersonal Skills.

B. Participants

The participants were approached from different government and private universities of Karachi, Pakistan and total participants were $N=251$ ($n=102$ males, $n=149$ females). All the participants belonged to 18-35 years.

C. Inclusion Criteria

For the present study the participants were selected based on following inclusion criteria:

Participant's age should be between 18-35. they must be using cellphone for at least past six months and their minimum education level should be intermediate or A level and must be enrolled in any government or private university.

D. Measures

- **Inform consent form.** Participants were requested to sign an informed consent before administrating the items of the selected scale and demographic form.
- **Demographic form.** The demographic form was being constructed to fulfill inclusion criteria of the research. In this form basic information about the participants questions were asked by providing the participants with demographic information form. Furthermore, few items were added to see the purpose of using of cellphone.
- **Cell Phone Addiction Scale (CPAS).** The questionnaire is originally developed in Korea by Korean AcadNurs in (2009) and it translated by Aamir Abbas, Afshan Chana, Mehdi Frishta, Javeria Abbas and Haider Naqvi at Agha Khan Hospital, Karachi in (2014). Cellphone addiction scale measures the psychological effect of cell phone usage, excessive cellphone usage which may put a person at risk of cell phone addiction. This scale analyses about three different constructs that contains 'withdrawal/tolerance', 'life dysfunction' and 'compulsion or persistence. The construct on withdrawal/tolerance and 'compulsion or persistence' has seven items each, and 'life dysfunction' has six items. The Phi correlation coefficient for the CPAS against the gold standard assessment was 0.62. Cronbach's alpha of 0.83 was obtained for internal consistency of each item.
- **Interpersonal Skills scale (IPS).** The interpersonal skills were measured by the subscale of Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by SyedaShida Batool and Ruhi Khalid at Beacon National University, Lahore in (2011). It consisted 8 items and on the scale item numbers are 18, 19, 21, 51, 52, 53, 54, and 55.

E. Procedure

The permission was taken from the affiliated department and the institution for the conduction of the research study and was collect data from the university students. Examining the nature of the study convenient sampling was being used. Firstly, participants were given a consent form to achieve their agreement for participation in the study. After seeking their consent questionnaires was being given to the participants that were: Interpersonal Skills Scale and Cell phone Addiction scale. The maximum time required to fill out the questionnaire was 5-10 minutes. After collecting data from 251 participants it was assembled and entered statistical tool SPSS for further analysis.

III. RESULTS

Variables	Male (n=102)		Female (n=149)		t	P	95 % CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
IPS	13.56	04.23	13.74	03.62	-0.33	0.73	-1.18	0.84
CPAS	54.53	11.57	52.51	12.37	1.30	0.19	-1.03	5.08

Table 1: Mean Standard deviation and T-value for gender on Interpersonal skills and Cellphone addiction.

Note: CI= Confidence interval; LL= Lower limit; UL= Upper limit IPS= Interpersonal skills; CPAS= Cellphone addiction Scale. There is no significant value between interpersonal skills and cellphone addiction on gender.

Variables	Joint Family (n=97)		Nuclear Family (n=153)		t	P	95 % CI	
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL
IPS	13.25	03.64	13.93	04.01	-1.34	0.17	-1.66	0.31
CPAS	55.19	12.92	52.16	11.38	1.94	0.05	-0.04	6.10

Table 2: Mean Standard deviation and T-value for joint and nuclear family on Interpersonal skills and Cellphone addiction

Note: CI= Confidence interval; LL= Lower limit; UL= Upper limit; IPS=Interpersonal skills; CPAS= Cellphone addiction Scale.

There is no significance value difference between interpersonal skills of joint and nuclear family. Whereas there is a significant difference in cellphone addiction, joint family has more cellphone addiction as compare to nuclear family.

Variables	Age range						F	η ²	i-j	Mean D (i-j)	S. E	95% CI	
	15-20 (n= 92)		21-25 (n=154)		31- 35 (n= 4)							LL	U. L
IPS	13.79	4.08	13.44	3.39	19.5	10.34	4.96	0.03*	15-20	-5.70*	1.95	-10.30	-1.16
CPAS	51.13	11.14	54.52	12.43	59.25	13.17	2.79		31-35> 21-25	5.70	1.95	01.10	10.30

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for interpersonal skills and cellphone addiction along age range.

Note: *p>.03, CI= Confidence interval, LL=Lower limit, UL= Upper limit, IPS= Interpersonal Skill, CPAS= Cellphone addiction Scale.

Analysis of (ANOVA) reveals about difference of age range on interpersonal skills and cellphone addiction. The above table 8 shows that there is weak positive correlation between cellphone addiction and interpersonal skills for age range.

Demographic Variables	Cellphone Addiction	Interpersonal Skills
Hours of Cellphone Usage	0.18**	0.12*
Number of Family Members	0.07	0.03
Earning Members	0.05	-0.02
Family Meals	-0.03	-0.05
Get together with relatives	-0.19	-0.08
Family Time	-0.08	-0.08
Money	0.11*	-0.03
Use Code	-0.03	-0.02
Cellphone Usage for Activities	0.01	0.13*

Table 4: Point Biserial correlation of Cellphone addiction and Interpersonal skills with demographics

Above table shows that there was a significant positive correlation between hours of cellphone usage and cellphone addiction and interpersonal skill. While, money spend on cellphone has a positive weak relationship with cellphone addiction and cellphone usage for other activities has weak positive correlation with interpersonal skills.

IV. DISCUSSION

The previous researches revealed that the excess use of the cell phone technology may underhandedly hinder proper interpersonal skill development (Wolak, Mitchell, & Finkelhor, 2003). It has been investigated that excessive use of cell phones are problems for the users (Block, 2008; King, Delfabbro, & Griffiths, 2012).

As current study, targeted student population and students are mostly loving to talk, more comfortable with on screen interaction rather than personal confront. They free from the pressure of professional lives and enjoying the freedom of being free. As males and females' study and work together also have same viewpoints about the usage of cell phone (Amaila Zahra, 2011) therefore, present study showed no significant difference between male and female on Cellphone addiction and Interpersonal skills of young adults.

Cell phone addiction is being common, youngsters undergo through a group pressure to remain interlink and approachable round the clock. (Medicine, 2008). By using cellphone, they remain in touch with their relatives, family members and friends circle. So, it can be adhered that cellphone has facilitated these interpersonal relationships which have been affected due to long distance or financial constraints.

Cell phone is a source of connection for these people, make it convenient and inform about their circumstances and their values. Collectively make it easy for adults to communicate with each in a variety of ways at any time or place (Auter, 2007; Boneva, Quinn, Kraut, Kiesler, & Shklovski, 2006). It is a source to develop, maintain and achieving a close personal connection with their relationships. The significance of face-to-face

communication is lost because the user is essentially just communicating to a screen.

Moreover, there is a significant positive correlation between hours of cellphone usage and cellphone addiction and interpersonal skill which shows that hours spending on phone has an influence on interpersonal skills of young adults. While, money spend on cellphone has a positive weak relationship with cellphone addiction and cellphone usage for other activities has weak positive correlation with interpersonal skills, showed that adults are not using their cell phones for just entertaining themselves but for useful means. Whereas, analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for interpersonal skills and cellphone addiction along age range presented weak positive correlation between cellphone addiction and interpersonal skills for age range.

Another finding was seen that, cell phone addiction is more high living in joint families than in nuclear family's system. While it was assumed that, living in joint system enhances interpersonal skills. It may be because of lack of time, or negligence of parents to their children. Parents spend most of their time with their elders and show less concern to youngsters. So that they are unable to interact face to face due to lack of confidence. Family dinners are typically considered as an opportunity for busy family members to have conversations, but this has been violated and replaced with cell phones (Corbett, 2009). Living in a joint family can be a little emotionally exhausting as there are more chances of getting involved into pointless arguments based on confusion, misinterpretation and jealousy amongst family members (Sandip, 2014). Grandparents usually tend to follow old traditions and expect children to follow them too. This leads to lack of modernization in the family and they tend to think less practically. Elders believe in old concepts too strongly which makes them less liberal and their children have difficulties managing with the modern world outside the society. Whereas in nuclear system children get full attention from their parents which enhance their capabilities and self-confidence, they are self-dependent and can be neutral towards anything as there is no psychological compression for any task/thing (Sandaine, 2016). Usually there is a clash of opinions in joint family system and mostly

dominated by elders, deficiency of open-mindedness and extreme stress in family members due to the conflict of different opinions. So, it may be the reason of high cell phone addiction living in joint family system.

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